

Natural Treatments for Glioblastoma: Studies and Research on Artemis, Green Tea and Angelica

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Introduction

When it comes to treating glioblastoma, a very aggressive malignant brain tumor, conventional treatments such as surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy have limitations. This has led many patients to seek alternative treatment options, including natural herbal treatments.

Among the plants studied for their anticancer potential are Artemis, green tea and angelica. These plants have been used for centuries in traditional medicines to treat a variety of diseases, including cancer.

These plants contain active compounds that have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and anti-cancer properties. As such, they can help reduce the growth and spread of cancer cells in the brain.

In this article, we will look at the most relevant studies on the use of Artemis, green tea and angelica in the treatment of glioblastoma. We will evaluate the potential benefits of these plants, as well as the precautions and limitations to consider when using them to treat this complex and difficult disease.

Method

After conducting an exhaustive search and selection of the most cited articles in the scientific literature¹ on the use of Artemis, green tea and angelica in the treatment of glioblastoma, we used LightPDF, ChatPDF,

¹ First, we used Google Scholar to find out the number of citations received by scientific articles, which allowed us to assess their relevance and impact in our field of research.

Next, we discovered Publish or Perish, a free software that allows you to perform bibliographic searches and analyze the results of scientific research. In particular, it makes it possible to measure the impact of an author, a journal or a scientific article using

ChatDOC, and ChatGPT, a computer language model developed by OpenAI. This is due to the fact that the author of this article suffers from glioblastoma. He is faced with fatigue and the side effects of treatment for this disease.

This software has been programmed to provide accurate and relevant information, based on evidence from the available scientific literature.

We are aware that the use of this software may raise questions regarding the objectivity and scientific rigour of this article. However, we have done our best to minimize any bias.

We hope this article will be useful for glioblastoma patients and their caregivers, as well as researchers and healthcare professionals seeking to better understand alternative treatment options for this serious and often fatal disease.

bibliometric indices such as the number of citations, the h-index or the impact factor.

The software provided us with other scientific articles sorted by their number of citations, which allowed us to select the most relevant articles for our text. This method of article selection is commonly used in scientific research to ensure the quality and relevance of cited sources.

Artemis: the therapeutic potential of artemisinin in the treatment of glioblastoma.

Summary : Several important findings have emerged from studies on the use of artemisinin and its derivatives, particularly dihydroartemisinin (DHA), in the treatment of glioblastoma:

1. **Inhibition of cell proliferation** : DHA has been shown to inhibit tumor cell proliferation, which is essential for slowing tumor growth.
2. **Autophagy activation** : Rather than inducing apoptosis (programmed cell death), DHA promotes autophagy, a process of cell degradation, which may be beneficial for controlling tumor growth.
3. **Synergy with temozolomide (TMZ)**: When combined with temozolomide, a standard drug for glioblastoma, DHA improved the efficacy of TMZ by reducing the median inhibitory concentration (IC50) of this drug, providing a more effective therapeutic strategy.
4. **Selective cytotoxic effects** : Studies have shown selective cytotoxic effects of artemisinin and its derivatives on tumor cells, thereby minimizing damage to healthy cells.
5. **Ferroptosis induction** : The use of artemisinin has been associated with the induction of ferroptosis, a type of regulated cell death characterized by the accumulation of lipid free radicals and reactive oxygen radicals (ROS) from iron metabolism.
6. **Involvement of specific proteins** : The underlying molecular mechanisms have been explored, revealing the impact of artemisinin on proteins such

as GPX4, HSPA5, ATF4, and others, thus providing crucial information on the signaling pathways involved in regulating tumor growth.

7. **Artemis-DNA-PKcs interaction** : A study has highlighted the crucial importance of the interaction between Artemis, a protein, and DNA-PKcs, a subunit of the DNA-PK kinase, in DNA repair processes, paving the way for the development of targeted therapies.
8. **CUSP9 approach** : A novel approach, called CUSP9, was introduced, combining nine existing drugs to target various tumour growth pathways, with a continuous low dose of temozolomide. This approach aims to improve tumor control while minimizing side effects, providing a new option for the treatment of recurrent glioblastoma.

In short, these discoveries offer promising new perspectives for the treatment of glioblastoma using artemisinin and its derivatives, highlighting specific mechanisms of action and innovative therapeutic approaches to fight this complex and aggressive disease.

Results: The study by Zhang et al. (2015) highlights the potential of dihydroartemisinin (DHA), an active metabolite of artemisinin extracted from *Artemisia annua* L., for the treatment of this form of brain tumor. The researchers observed that DHA had the ability to inhibit tumor cell proliferation by primarily inducing autophagy, a process of cell degradation, rather than apoptosis. In addition, when combined with temozolomide (TMZ), a drug commonly used for this disease, DHA significantly reduced the median inhibitory concentration (IC50) of TMZ, enhancing its efficacy. This synergy was also observed in tumor-bearing mice, suggesting that DHA may offer a promising pathway for the treatment of this aggressive tumor.

The study by Chen et al. (2019) explores the use of artemisinin and its derivatives, particularly DHA, against glioblastoma. The results highlight selective cytotoxic effects on tumor cells by inducing a type of regulated cell death called "ferroptosis". This cell death is characterized by the accumulation of lipid peroxidation products and reactive oxygen radicals (ROS) from iron metabolism. The study also details the molecular mechanisms involved, highlighting the impact of artemisinin on proteins such as GPX4, HSPA5, ATF4, and others. In vivo experiments have confirmed these effects, paving the way for new approaches for the treatment of this tumor.

Drouet et al. (2006) conducted an in-depth study on the interaction between Artemis, a protein, and DNA-PKcs, a subunit of the DNA-PK kinase, in the context of DNA repair. The researchers demonstrated that DNA-PKcs kinase activity is essential for maintaining the association between Artemis and DNA-PKcs when they bind to the ends of damaged DNA in vitro. This discovery highlights the crucial importance of the interaction between these proteins in DNA repair processes, which could have important implications for the development of targeted therapies in the future.

The study by Yi et al. (2020) also looked at the effect of DHA on this tumor, focusing on its selective cytotoxic effect on tumor cells compared to normal cells. The researchers found that glioblastoma cells had significantly higher expression of transferrin receptors (TfR), involved in iron metabolism, compared to normal cells. The effect of DHA has been attributed to the induction of ferroptosis, characterized by the accumulation of lipid free radicals and iron dependence. The results showed a significant decrease in the GPX4 enzyme, essential for suppressing lipid free radical buildup, in glioblastoma cells treated with DHA. This study also revealed an increase in the levels of total free radicals and lipid free radicals in these cells. Notably, inhibition of ferroptosis with a specific inhibitor called ferrostatin-1 was able to reverse the effect of DHA, paving the way for future research on this association between ferroptosis and polyamines.

The paper by Kast et al. (2013) introduces an innovative approach for the treatment of recurrent glioblastoma, an aggressive brain tumor. This approach, dubbed CUSP9, combines nine drugs already available on the market, targeting various tumor growth pathways, with a continuous low dose of temozolomide, a drug commonly used in the treatment of this disease. Among the drugs included in this plan, artesunate, derived from artemisinin, is integrated to target the NK-1R receptor, which plays a role in tumor growth. The main goal of CUSP9 is to improve tumor control while minimizing side effects, thereby improving patients' quality of life. This innovative approach opens up new perspectives in the treatment of recurrent glioblastoma, a disease for which there is currently no accepted standard treatment.

Finally, another study by Vengoji et al. (2018) highlights a study conducted by Muhammad et al., which talks about the effectiveness of artemisinin in the fight against glioblastoma. This time, artemisinin was extracted from the leaves of *Artemisia argyi*, also known as "silvery wormwood". The study focused on the effect of

jaceosidine, a compound derived from artemisinin, on tumor cells. The results showed that jaceosidine treatment inhibited tumor cell proliferation, caused cell cycle arrest in the G2/M phase and stimulated apoptosis. This increase in apoptosis was associated with increased expression of proapoptotic proteins such as Bax and p53, as well as alterations in the mitochondrial membrane, release of cytochrome C into the cytoplasm, and activation of caspase-3. These findings reinforce the idea that artemisinin and its derivatives have promising potential in the treatment of glioblastoma by directly targeting tumor cells.

Conclusion: The studies reviewed highlight the therapeutic potential of artemisinin and its derivatives, particularly DHA, in the fight against glioblastoma. These compounds have shown selective cytotoxic effects on tumor cells, inducing ferroptosis and specifically targeting brain tumors through the expression of specific receptors. In addition, the interaction between Artemis and DNA-PKcs has been highlighted in DNA repair, suggesting new avenues for the development of targeted therapies. The CUSP9 approach also offers hope for the treatment of recurrent glioblastoma by combining several existing drugs. Overall, this research paves the way for innovative strategies to address this dreaded and complex disease, while offering new perspectives for the treatment of glioblastoma.

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Green tea: the promising potential of EGCG in green tea

Abstract: Several scientific articles explore the potential of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), a polyphenol found in green tea, in the treatment of glioblastoma. The following is a general analysis of these studies:

- Potential role of EGCG in the treatment of glioblastoma :** Studies suggest that EGCG may have a promising role in the treatment of glioblastoma by acting as an adjuvant to conventional treatments such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy. It is noted that EGCG has well-studied bioactive properties, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, which are relevant in the context of cancer.
- Potentiation of chemotherapy efficacy :** EGCG appears to increase the sensitivity of tumor cells to some common anticancer drugs, which may improve the effectiveness of chemotherapy while reducing unwanted side effects.
- Role as a radiosensitizer :** EGCG may increase the effectiveness of radiation therapy by inducing programmed cell death (apoptosis) and necrosis of cancer cells, which may improve local tumor control.
- Protection against adverse side effects :** EGCG appears to have the ability to reduce chemotherapy-

and radiation-induced toxicity, which may improve patients' tolerance to these aggressive treatments.

- Interaction with other drugs :** It is noted that EGCG may have antagonistic interactions with some anticancer drugs, highlighting the need for further research to understand its potential role as an adjuvant.
- Targeting tumor cell metabolism :** Some studies indicate that EGCG may target tumor cell metabolism, including inhibiting the activity of certain enzymes, which may be relevant in the treatment of glioblastoma.
- Inhibition of matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs):** EGCG, in particular, appears to be effective in inhibiting MMPs, which play a key role in tumor invasion and metastasis.

Results: The paper by Lecumberri et al. (2013) explores with interest the potential role of epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG), an abundant polyphenol found in green tea, as a promising adjuvant in the treatment of glioblastoma. The research compiled in this article brings together the most recent evidence on the use of EGCG in conjunction with chemotherapy and radiation therapy in an attempt to improve clinical outcomes.

EGCG is a natural compound with well-studied bioactive properties, including its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. This polyphenol has attracted particular interest because of its potential anti-cancer effects. In the context of glioblastoma, the article explores how EGCG could strengthen the therapeutic arsenal against this aggressive tumor.

The first aspect addressed is the ability of EGCG to potentiate the effectiveness of chemotherapy. Research has shown that EGCG can make tumor cells more sensitive to some commonly used anticancer drugs, such as 5-fluorouracil, cisplatin, and tamoxifen. In addition, it can change the pharmacokinetics of these drugs, increasing their concentration inside cancer cells. This synergistic action could potentially improve the effectiveness of chemotherapy while reducing the dose needed, which could reduce unwanted side effects.

The second aspect studied is the role of EGCG as a radiosensitizer. Preclinical data suggest that EGCG may increase the effectiveness of radiotherapy by inducing more apoptosis (programmed cell death) and necrosis in cancer cells. Clinical trials have also shown promising results from the use of EGCG in conjunction with

radiotherapy for the treatment of glioblastoma multiforme and other types of cancer. This approach could potentially improve local tumor control.

Finally, the article discusses the properties of EGCG as a protective agent against the adverse side effects of chemotherapy and radiotherapy. EGCG appears to have the ability to reduce gastrointestinal, renal, cardiac, auditory and pulmonary toxicity induced by these aggressive treatments. The antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of EGCG are highlighted to explain these protective effects.

However, it is important to note that antagonistic interactions with some anticancer drugs have been observed. These observations underscore the need for further research, particularly at a clinical level, to better understand the potential role of EGCG as an adjuvant in the treatment of glioblastoma. In short, this article opens interesting perspectives to improve the management of glioblastoma through the use of EGCG in addition to conventional treatments.

Another article (McLaughlin et al., 2006) examines the potential use of epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCg) in the treatment of glioblastoma. The research focuses on radioresistance in glioblastoma cells and explores the effect of EGCg on their response to radiotherapy.

The results indicate that low-dose irradiation partially inhibits the growth of glioblastoma cells, but this inhibition does not appear to be due to caspase-mediated apoptosis. Irradiation also stimulates the expression of Survivin, an anti-apoptotic protein, as well as RhoA and Caveoline-1, proteins involved in regulating cell survival and proliferation.

The paper reveals that the increased expression of survivine confers resistance to irradiation, while the overexpression of RhoA makes cells more sensitive to radiotherapy. EGCg is effective in inhibiting the proliferation of glioblastoma cells in a dose-dependent manner. In addition, it does not antagonize the cytoprotective effect of Survivin. When cells overexpress survivine and are exposed to EGCg, they become sensitive to irradiation, and RhoA expression is down-regulated.

In conclusion, EGCg could be a promising option to improve the effectiveness of radiotherapy in the treatment of glioblastoma. This research suggests that the use of EGCg in combination with radiotherapy could help overcome glioblastoma cell radioresistance, paving

the way for new therapeutic approaches for this complex disease.

The article by Yang et al. (2009) suggests that epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), may have an interest in the treatment of glioblastoma. Glioblastoma is highly dependent on glucose metabolism. However, many current therapies target glycolysis (glucose metabolism) rather than glutamine metabolism, which also plays a key role in tumor cell survival.

The study reveals that EGCG inhibits the activity of glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH), an enzyme involved in glutamine metabolism. When glioblastoma cells are deprived of glucose, inhibition of GDH by EGCG increases cell mortality. In addition, when EGCG is combined with drugs that limit glucose metabolism, such as Akt inhibitors or 2-deoxyglucose (2-DG), it increases the effect of these drugs on cell death.

These results suggest that EGCG could be a potential adjunct in the treatment of glioblastoma, particularly in combination with therapies that target glucose metabolism. This opens up the possibility of exploiting alternative metabolic pathways, such as glutamine, to improve the effectiveness of glioblastoma treatments. However, further clinical studies would be needed to confirm these observations and determine the efficacy of EGCG in the treatment of glioblastoma in patients.

In addition, the study by Demeule et al. (2000) explores the effects of certain active components present in natural products, including green tea polyphenols, on the activities of matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs). MMPs play a crucial role in tumor invasion and metastasis, making them potential targets in the fight against cancer. The results of the study show that among the different compounds tested, green tea polyphenols, particularly epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), are the most effective at inhibiting MMP-2, MMP-9 and MMP-12.

Green tea has long been associated with anti-cancer properties, and this study reinforces the idea that the polyphenols it contains may play a beneficial role in cancer prevention or treatment. In addition, green tea polyphenols have shown their specificity by not affecting pancreatic elastase, suggesting that their effects on MMPs are targeted.

The study also suggests that green tea polyphenols may inhibit proMMP-2 activation, which could have important implications for regulating these enzymes in the tumor context.

In summary, green tea polyphenols, particularly EGCG, have a high potential to inhibit MMPs, which could help reduce the invasion and spread of cancer cells. These results highlight the value of further research into the use of natural compounds in green tea in the fight against cancer.

The study by Golden et al. (2009) examined the effects of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) and other polyphenols present in green tea on the efficacy of a proteasome inhibitor called bortezomib (BZM) in the treatment of multiple myeloma and glioblastoma, both in the laboratory (in vitro) and in mice (in vivo). Contrary to expectations, the results revealed that these components of green tea, particularly EGCG, had an antagonistic effect on BZM. This means that they effectively prevented BZM-induced cell death, compromising its effectiveness as an anticancer agent.

This antagonism phenomenon was specific to boronic acid-containing proteasome inhibitors, such as BZM, and was not observed with other proteasome inhibitors that did not contain this chemical function. The researchers also found that this interaction occurred at EGCG concentrations that can be reached in humans after consuming green tea or supplements containing these polyphenols.

These findings highlight the importance of understanding the potential interactions between compounds found in foods, such as green tea polyphenols, and drugs used in cancer treatment. In the context of the treatment of glioblastoma and multiple myeloma, it is crucial to take this interaction into account to avoid compromising the effectiveness of the drugs.

The article by Ahn et al. (1999) examines the potential value of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), in the context of anticancer and anti-atherosclerotic activity. The researchers conducted a study using rat vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMC) to explore how EGCG affects cell signaling induced by various growth factors, such as PDGF-BB, EGF, angiotensin II, and calf fetal serum (FCS).

Their results showed that EGCG had an inhibitory effect on signaling protein activation, specifically PDGF-BB-induced activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAP kinases). In addition, EGCG inhibited phosphorylation of PDGF-R β , a protein involved in regulating cell growth.

In addition, EGCG demonstrated an ability to inhibit cell growth, DNA synthesis and cell colony formation in cancer cells (A172) and NIH 3T3 cells transferred with the

simian v-sis gene. This suggests that EGCG may have anticancer potential by preventing the growth and proliferation of cancer cells, particularly those activated by PDGF-R β .

The article also highlights the complexity of EGCG's mechanisms of action, noting that its effectiveness can vary depending on concentration, growth factor type and cellular context.

In conclusion, this study suggests that green tea EGCG may have potential anticancer properties by specifically targeting PDGF-R β -induced cell signaling, which could contribute to the prevention or treatment of certain forms of cancer, particularly those associated with PDGF-R β overexpression. However, more research is needed to confirm these findings and fully understand the mechanisms of action of EGCG in a clinical setting.

The article by Annabi (2002) highlights the potential beneficial effect of green tea, particularly EGCg (epigallocatechin gallate), in the fight against glioblastoma, a type of aggressive brain cancer. The researchers studied glioblastoma U-87 cells to understand the mechanisms involved in the activation of proMMP-2, a protein linked to tumor invasion. They found that EGCg had a significant impact on these processes.

In the presence of EGCg, the amount of proMMP-2 secreted by cells decreased, while intracellular levels of proMMP-2 increased. This suggests that EGCg regulates the secretion of proMMP-2 and inhibits its activation. In addition, the study showed that EGCg specifically targets MT1-MMP, a protease associated with proMMP-2 activation, suggesting a mechanism of direct action of EGCg on this protein.

This research highlights the potential of green tea and its compounds, such as EGCg, as anticancer agents, particularly in the context of glioblastoma. The results pave the way for future investigations into the precise mechanisms by which gCGE exerts its beneficial effects against this form of brain cancer.

The study by Sachinidis et al. (2000) highlights the potential interest of green tea, in particular EGCG (epigallocatechin gallate), in the prevention of glioblastoma. The researchers conducted experimental studies to examine the effects of compounds found in green tea on glioblastoma cells and underlying mechanisms.

They found that EGCG and other catechins in green tea were able to inhibit the activity of platelet-derived growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase (PDGF-R β). This receptor is involved in cell growth and proliferation, and its hyperactivation has been associated with the development of certain cancers, including glioblastomas. EGCG, at a concentration of 50 μ M, showed significant inhibition of tyrosine phosphorylation of PDGF-R β induced by platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF-BB).

In addition, the researchers observed that EGCG and other catechins inhibited the formation of multicellular glioblastoma cell spheroids in agar culture medium. This inhibition of spheroid formation indicates a potentially preventive effect against tumor growth.

The paper suggests that inhibition of PDGF-R β tyrosine kinase activity by EGCG and other green tea catechins may help reduce the risk of developing certain types of cancer, including glioblastoma. These findings pave the way for future research into the potential use of green tea compounds in cancer prevention, particularly cancers associated with hyperactivation of growth factor receptors.

Finally, the study by Chen et al. (2011) examines the effect of EGCG, a component of green tea, on the therapeutic efficacy of temozolomide (TMZ) in the treatment of glioblastomas.

The researchers found that EGCG is able to improve the effectiveness of TMZ by inhibiting a protein called GRP78, which plays a key role in the stress response of the endoplasmic reticulum. When GRP78 is inhibited, tumor cells become more sensitive to the cytotoxic effects of TMZ.

The results of the in vitro and in vivo studies showed that EGCG, administered in combination with TMZ, significantly prolonged the survival of mice with glioblastomas. This combination therapy also induced increased apoptosis of tumor cells.

In summary, this research highlights the potential of EGCG to improve the effectiveness of glioblastoma treatment in combination with TMZ.

Conclusion: The scientific studies cited shed valuable light on the potential role of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), a polyphenol found in green tea, in the treatment of glioblastoma. These studies explore various aspects of EGCG use as a therapeutic adjuvant, including its impact on chemotherapy, radiotherapy, cellular metabolism, and matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)

regulation. Although promising results have been observed, it is essential to highlight the need for further research, especially at a clinical level, to fully validate the efficacy of EGCG in the treatment of glioblastoma. These studies open up exciting new perspectives to improve the management of this complex disease by harnessing the potential of EGCG in combination with conventional treatments.

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Angelica: The n-butylidenephthalide of Angelica sinensis

Summary : Angelica sinensis and its active compound, n-butylidenephthalide (BP), have demonstrated several significant impacts in the treatment of glioblastoma multiforme (GBM):

- 1. Induction of tumor cell apoptosis:** Angelica sinensis and BP have the ability to induce apoptosis, a process of programmed cell death, in GBM tumor cells. This helps reduce tumor growth and eliminate cancer cells.
- 2. Inhibition of tumor growth:** These substances have been shown to be effective in inhibiting the growth of malignant brain tumors, especially GBM. They work by stopping the cell cycle of tumor cells, which hinders their multiplication.
- 3. Synergy with temozolomide (TMZ):** Angelica sinensis and BP may work synergistically with temozolomide (TMZ), a drug commonly used in the treatment of GBM. This synergy enhances the effectiveness of TMZ in the destruction of tumor cells.
- 4. Increased radiosensitivity:** These substances increase the sensitivity of GBM tumor cells to

radiation therapy, which means that radiation treatments may be more effective in the presence of Angelica sinensis or BP.

- 5. Cancer stem cell reduction:** Angelica sinensis has the ability to reduce the cancer stem cell population in the GBM. Cancer stem cells are often responsible for treatment resistance and relapse.
- 6. Alteration of the blood-brain barrier:** These substances can change the permeability of the blood-brain barrier, making it easier for drugs and treatments to access the brain, where the tumour is located.

These impacts suggest that the potential use of Angelica sinensis, particularly the compound BP, could have a significant impact on the effectiveness of GBM treatments. However, it is important to note that more research is needed to fully assess the efficacy and safety of these approaches in the treatment of GBM.

Results:

In the study by Vengoji et al. (2018) Angelica sinensis root extracts are defined as having demonstrated effects such as induction of tumor cell apoptosis, inhibition of tumor growth, synergy with temozolomide (TMZ), increased radiosensitivity, reduction of cancer stem cells and modification of blood-brain barrier permeability to facilitate access to treatments. These findings suggest a potential interest of Angelica sinensis in the treatment of GBM.

According to Wang et al. (2019), chloroform extracts of angelica demonstrated inhibition of glioma cell proliferation, cell cycle arrest in the G0-G1 phase and induction of apoptosis. In addition, a major component of angelica, butylidenephthalide (BP), has shown antitumor effects by inhibiting glioma cell proliferation and inducing apoptosis through different signaling pathways.

In addition, Tsai et al. (2005) explain that angelica (Angelica sinensis) exhibits antitumor effects on malignant glioblastomas of the brain. Angelica showed inhibitory effects on brain tumor cell growth in vitro and in vivo, without toxicity to normal fibroblasts. It was also able to reduce the growth of malignant brain tumors of human and rat origin, as well as reduce the volume of glioblastomas in situ, resulting in a significant prolongation of survival of treated subjects.

Angelica worked by stopping the cell cycle and inducing apoptosis of GBM tumor cells. It increased the

expression of cell cycle inhibitory proteins and decreased the phosphorylation of Rb proteins, leading to cell cycle arrest in the G0-G1 phase. In addition, it activated apoptotic pathways, increasing the expression of proteins associated with apoptosis. The results showed that angelica can induce apoptosis of GBM tumor cells by p53-dependent and independent pathways.

In 2006, the same team published a study (Tsai et al., 2006) which explains that angelica is a traditional Chinese medicinal plant that has been used for centuries to treat various diseases. The compound n-butylidenephthalide (BP) is one of the main active components of angelica. Previous studies have shown that BP has anti-inflammatory, antithrombotic and neuroprotective properties. In this study, researchers examined the effects of BP on the growth of glioblastoma multiforme tumor cells in vitro and in vivo. The results showed that BP inhibited tumor cell growth and induced apoptosis, a process of programmed cell death. What's more, BP also reduced the formation of new blood vessels in tumors, which is important because tumors need new blood vessels to grow. These results suggest that angelica, particularly BP, could be used as a novel anti-brain tumor drug for the treatment of glioblastoma multiforme. However, further studies are needed to assess the efficacy and safety of angelica in patients with glioblastoma multiforme.

According to Lin et al. (2008), angelica contains a compound called n-butylidenephthalide (BP) that has a dramatic antitumor effect on malignant brain tumors, particularly glioblastoma multiforme (GBM). Studies have shown that BP can induce apoptosis (programmed cell death) of GBM tumor cells by increasing the expression of the Nur77 protein.

The results of studies show that the compound N-Butylidenephthalide (BP), extracted from angelica, exhibits antitumor effects on brain tumors of glioblastoma multiforme. This study demonstrated that BP induced apoptosis of glioblastoma multiforme cancer cells, both in vitro and in vivo. In addition, BP was found to reduce tumor growth to a significant incidence and prolong survival rates.

Conclusion: Studies of *Angelica sinensis*, including its root extracts and the compound n-butylidenephthalide (BP), have shown promising effects in the treatment of glioblastoma multiforme (GBM). These effects include induction of tumor cell apoptosis, inhibition of tumor growth, synergy with temozolomide (TMZ), increase in radiosensitivity, reduction of cancer stem cells, and

alteration of blood-brain barrier permeability. These findings suggest a strong potential of *Angelica sinensis*, particularly the compound BP, as a treatment option for GBM. However, more studies are needed to assess its efficacy and safety in patients with this aggressive brain tumor.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, natural treatments based on Artemis, green tea and angelica can offer great potential for the treatment of glioblastoma. These plants have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer properties that can help reduce the growth and spread of cancer cells.

However, the studies reported in this context refer to research conducted on preclinical models of tumors, either in vitro (in cell culture) or in vivo (in laboratory animals). These models are used to study the biological mechanisms underlying tumor formation and

progression, as well as to test the effectiveness of potential new treatments.

In vitro studies involve culturing tumor cells in a controlled laboratory environment, where researchers can examine how cells behave and respond to different treatments or stimuli. These studies can provide valuable insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying tumor growth, as well as the effect of drugs or therapeutic interventions on these mechanisms.

In vivo studies, on the other hand, involve the use of animal models to simulate the conditions of a tumor in the human body. Animals are usually inoculated with tumor cells, either directly into the tumor or from a distant site to observe the spread of the cells. These studies can provide information about how effective a treatment is on the tumour itself, as well as its effects on the body as a whole.

Overall, preclinical studies in in vitro or in vivo tumors are crucial for oncology research, as they allow researchers to understand disease mechanisms and develop potential new treatments before moving on to human clinical trials.

Nevertheless, although preclinical studies in vitro or in vivo tumors are crucial to understanding the mechanisms of the disease and to developing potential new treatments, it is important to emphasize that there is still a need for clinical trials in humans to evaluate the efficacy and safety of these treatments.

Results from preclinical models do not always guarantee similar results in humans due to differences between the

biological systems of preclinical and human models. It is therefore important to conduct well-controlled clinical trials to evaluate the effects of treatments in cancer patients.

In addition, clinical trials also help determine optimal doses of treatment, potential side effects, and interactions with other treatments or medications the patient may be taking. This allows healthcare professionals to recommend the most appropriate treatments for each patient based on their individual profile.

In sum, although preclinical studies are essential for oncology research, it is important to conduct clinical trials in humans to evaluate the efficacy and safety of potential treatments before recommending them on a large scale for the treatment of cancer patients.

It is also important to note that there are negative opinions about these natural treatments in some studies that have been less cited. It is therefore important to continue conducting research to better understand how these plants work and define safe and effective doses for glioblastoma patients.

In sum, although these natural treatments can offer significant benefits for the treatment of glioblastoma, it is important not to consider these plants as a complete alternative to conventional treatments. Patients should always consult their doctor before taking herbal supplements and follow the recommendations of their medical team to achieve the best possible outcome in their treatment.